

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14106587

Predictors of Students' Academic Achievement in Entrepreneurship Education in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State, Nigeria

Opara, Eucharia, A. & Prof. Ukaigwe, P. C

**Department of Educational Management and Planning,
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria
Email: euchariaopara54@gmail.com
Email: ukaigwep17@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship is an important component for any nation aspiring to be competitive in the knowledge-based global market due to the fact that it has been generally viewed as a method of promoting economic growth, creativity, and innovation. This study investigated the predictors of students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in public senior secondary school in Rivers State, Nigeria. Three objectives and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A correlational survey design was adopted. The Population of the study consisted of all 6,893 teachers in 286 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The sample of this study comprised of 689 teachers of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, through a proportionate random sampling technique. This represents 10% of the entire population. A 20 item self-designed questionnaire titled "Predictors of Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire (PSAAQ) and Entrepreneurial Education Achievement Questionnaire (EEAQ)" was used for data collection. The reliability indices of the two instruments yielded 0.88 and 0.92 respectively. Simple regression analysis was used in answering the research questions, while T-test associated with simple regression was implored in testing the hypotheses. The outcome of the analysis showed that there is a significant relationship between teaching/learning facilities, school climate, teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study concluded that when there is adequate and available teaching and learning facilities in schools, it boosts learning among students, thereby enhancing their academic achievement. Also, favourable climate will go a long way to enhance students' academic achievement, which have tendency of advancing teaching and learning.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Academic Achievement, Teaching/Learning Facilities, School Climate, Teaching Strategy

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is an important component for any nation aspiring to be competitive in the knowledge-based global market due to the fact that it has been generally viewed as a method of promoting economic growth, creativity, and innovation. This view has led to a growing interest in developing educational programmes that encourage and enhance entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship has been recognized as a good alternative to unemployment, underemployment and poverty among the young ones, especially in instances where educated individuals cannot find jobs (Brownhilder, 2014). It is perceived as been vital to economic growth through increase in manpower contribution to output.

Entrepreneurial education as noted by Osaat and Osaat (2013) is the education that deals with the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills. It is the process whereby entrepreneurial skills are acquired for undertaking a business initiative with the aim of achieving self-employment, self-reliance, self-sustenance and the overall individual and society development, which has tendency of making one an employer of labour. Ukala (2018) in her research work used these concepts interchangeably to mean the same as trade education, entrepreneurial education, vocational education, career education, and technical education.

According to Ukaigwe (2017) a secondary school is that level of education, which provides secondary education between the ages of 11 and 19 depending on location after primary school and before higher education. Ukala (2018); FRN (2013) stated that the new Senior Secondary Education Curriculum structure comprised of five compulsory core subjects that must be offered by all students as; English Language, General Mathematics, Computer Studies, Civic Education/Christian Religious Studies/Islamic Studies and Trade/Entrepreneurial Studies. Further, FRN (2013); Igocharacha, Ugochi, Okolo, and Egbuionu (2017); Ukala (2018) listed the following as Entrepreneurial subjects; agricultural crop production, crop production and sales, driving career (cars, keke, and okada), iron and steel production, money collection (daily/monthly ususu), paper and pulp, petroleum/petrochemical production, tobacco production, soap and detergent production, wood treatment, petty trading, car wash, waste management technology, information management technology, melting, weaving (clothe and mat), bead making, wood carving, canoe carving, pottery, artistic, singing, dancing, music, tattoo or body arts, hunting, bakery, shoe making, sign writing, photographing, fashion design, fabrication etc.

Review of Related Literature

Student academic achievement as it applies to this research will be interchangeably referred to as student academic performance, academic outcome, outcome, performance etc. Steinmayr, MeiBner, Weidinger, and Wirthwein, (2015) stated that academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of the activities in instructional environment, specifically in school, college and university, thus, positive academic performance is the child's ability and effort to score high in school subjects or courses of instruction. While low achievement score might indicate that there are concerned areas that an individual should improve on, or that a subject should be repeated (Ayanyemi, 2023). As such, there are factors that predict high or low students' academic achievement.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework of predictors of students' academic achievement

Predictors of Students' Academic Achievement

Predictors of students' academic achievement are those factors that anticipates or that foretells students' achievement. A look into various documents on the predictors of student academic achievement it was found according to Barca *et al.* (2003 as cited in Hector 2015) learning approaches are the key determinants of academic performance. According to Georgia Department of Education (GADOE) (2016 as cited in Knapper 2017) research has demonstrated that school environment or school climate impacts student engagement, student achievement and the development of positive social skills amongst students. Also, improvement in the academic performance of students is dependent on a combination of teacher, student, school and parental factors; Environmental, Personal, Social, Psychological and economic factors (Sign, Priteshni, & Mohammed, 2016). Interest in pursuing a subject, co-curricular activities, nationality of a student and gender affect the academic performance of a student. Positive classroom environment has also been found as determining factor of academic performance of students (Meindinyo & Ikurite, 2017)

Concept of Teaching Strategy

Instructional strategy are the instructional materials and procedures that enable students to achieve the learning outcomes (Hill & Jordan, 2021). According to Marzano *et al.* (2001 as cited in Knapper 2017) in order to increase student achievement teachers must engage in "high-yields", instructional strategies that consist of having students' identify similarities and differences, summarize and take notes, complete homework, create nonlinguistic representations, such as graphic organizers and participate in cooperative learning groups. According to Dean (2019) many teaching strategies work for any classroom, no matter what the age of the students or the subject, when a teacher implements a combination of effective teaching strategies, their students have more opportunities to perform better in class.

Concept of Teaching and Learning Facilities

FRN (2004 as cited in Opara (2018) noted that "the quality of any educational system is determined by the quality of the teaching-learning process". Ukaigwe (2020) noted that Web 2.00 technologies allow individuals to open interactive online platform such as form and virtual classrooms where teachers and students can interact by posting their comments and questions for their teachers to respond and answer respectively. On the other hand, Ordu (2021) stated that teachers use teaching aids to enhance classroom instruction, extract learners' attention and create a motivation to learn. Some of these teaching aids are (book, chalk board, picture), or objects (specimen, map, glove) that help the teacher to effortlessly carry out the teaching-learning process.

The study of Opara, Okwai, and Ugwuchi-Ishiaya, (2023) which centered on teaching-learning facilities noted that instructional facilities are the direct teaching-learning facilities, through emerging technologies and innovations the operational system of education has changed politically and administratively via the introduction of new methods of education delivery where teachers would have to adapt to the use of internet through Flip grid, Whatsapp, Twitter, Skype, MySpace, Yahoo Messenger to reach out to children in collaboration with their parents for the purpose of instilling knowledge, ideas through audio, sharing of photos and videos by users. Adalikwu and Lordpilgh (2013) found that in Nigeria, instructional materials have a significant impact on academic performance. The use of instructional materials assists students to understand the concept of a subject better. As a result of this, students who are taught with instructional materials perform better than students taught without instructional materials.

Concept of School Climate

Galvez-Nieto, Polamco –Levicam, Trizano-Hermosilla, and Beltran –Veliz (2022) stated that school climate refers to the quality of school relationships and the character of school life and has been used as a predictor or outcome variable in various empirical studies at the school level. They stated also that the definition of school climate has to do with social and organisational aspects, including the relationships between school members and the values and norms shared by the educational institutions. Berkowitz, Moore, Astor, and Benbenishty, (2017) asserted that supportive school and classroom climate can positively influence the academic outcomes of students, thus potentially reducing academic achievement gaps between students and schools of different socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds.

Review of Related Empirical studies

A look into the work carried out by Wu and Tian (2022) examined predictors of entrepreneurship intention among students in vocational colleges: a structural equation modeling approach. The outcome of their analysis revealed that both entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial attitudes serve as significant predictors of entrepreneurial interest. The present study extended further by looking at teaching and learning facilities; school climate and teaching strategy as possible predictors of students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in public secondary schools. Similarly,

Abaidoo (2018) investigated factors contributing to academic performance of students in Junior High School. The study was conducted primarily to assess the factors contributing to improvement in academic performance of Junior High Students (JHS) in Gomoa Manso Basic School which is in the Gomo –East District in the central Region of Ghana. It was revealed from the analysis that academic performance of students improved as a result of completion of syllabus, frequent feedback to students and given students special attention. This entails that teachers' role, especially as regards teaching strategy is vital to students' performance. However, the present examined how teaching strategy among other variables predicts students' performance in entrepreneurship education.

Statement of the Problem

Education is the most significant instrument for any fundamental change in a nation especially in this era of poverty reduction, wealth creation and need for higher standard of living. Hence, there is need for the introduction of entrepreneurial education in public senior secondary schools in Nigeria. In Rivers State public secondary schools, education is delivered through several subjects that are expected to have been taught appropriately with various performance assessments carried out routinely and results issued out to students. Despite the introduction of this programme with its attendant goal expectations, it has been observed that the desirable effect and intent on students to be enterprisers is not encouraging. This evidence is observed through their low academic achievement scores in entrepreneurial subjects.

Students' academic achievement is notable in students being successful in subjects offered in different schools, but often, in the sequence of acquiring successful academic achievement in trade subjects learnt, it is observed by the researcher that students' academic achievement everywhere and especially those in the Rivers State senior secondary schools have being associated with low grades and the extent differs from school to school and is equally shown in students lack of skills and intention to be enterprisers. However, the perceived predictors of students' academic achievement such as teaching and learning facilities, school climate and teaching strategy could affect entrepreneurial education delivery in schools either negatively or positively, which is what this study attempts to uncover. This research therefore, considers how students' performance in entrepreneurship education can be predicted by teaching and learning facilities; school climate and teaching strategy in public senior secondary schools, which have not been adequately investigated.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the predictors of students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in public senior secondary school in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate the extent teaching and learning facilities predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurial education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. ascertain the extent school climate predict student academic achievement in entrepreneurial education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
3. investigate the extent teaching strategy predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurial education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- a) To what extent does teaching and learning facilities predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- b) To what extent does school climate predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?

- c) To what extent does teaching strategy predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

5. There is no significant relationship between teaching/learning facilities and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
6. There is no significant relationship between school climate and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
7. There is no significant relationship between teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted correlational survey research design. The population of the study comprised of all 6,893 teachers in 286 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. A proportionate random sampling technique was adopted in selecting a sample of 689 teachers of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. This represents 10% of the entire population. A 20-item self-designed questionnaire titled "Predictors of Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire (PSAAQ) and Entrepreneurial Education Achievement Questionnaire (EEAQ)" was used to generate information for the study.

PSAAQ and EEAQ consists of two sections A and B. Section A contained simple questions on demographic variables while section B, consists of 20 questions designed to illicit responses to three research questions. Responses to items on each section were coded along a modified four likert Scale of Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2) and Very Low Extent (1). The reliability indices of the instruments were established using the Cronbach Alpha. It yielded 0.88 and 0.92 respectively, showing that the instruments were strongly reliable. Data obtained from the administered instrument were analyzed using SPSS version 25. In answering the research questions, simple regression analysis was used while t-test associated with simple regression was implored in testing the hypotheses formulated for the study, at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *To what extent does teaching and learning facilities predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent teaching and learning facilities predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.923 ^a	.852	.852	1.97317	.852	3956.005	1	688	.000

Table 1 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.923 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.852. This shows to a high extent that students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria is positively predicted by teaching and learning facilities. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 85.2% change in students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria can be predicted by teaching and learning facilities, while 14.8% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does school climate predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent school climate predicts students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.879 _a	.773	.772	2.44350	.773	2340.279	1	688	.000

Table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.879 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.773. This shows to a high extent that students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria is positively predicted by school climate. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 77.3% change in students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria can be predicted by school climate, while 22.7% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Three *To what extent does teaching strategy predict students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent teaching strategy predicts to students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.809 _a	.655	.655	3.00999	.655	1307.669	1	688	.000

Table 3 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.809 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.655. This shows to a high extent that students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria is positively predicted by teaching strategy. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 65.5% change in students' academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria can be predicted by teaching strategy, while 34.5% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study.

Testing of Hypotheses

The null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested using t-test associated with simple regression, which is used for prediction.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between teaching/learning facilities and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4: t-test associated with simple Regression on the relationship between teaching and learning facilities and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.051	.454		4.521	.000
	Teaching and Learning Facilities	.939	.015	.923	62.897	.000

Table 4 revealed that teaching and learning facilities is related with entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria by 0.923. The t-test value 62.897 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between teaching/learning facilities and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between school climate and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 5: t-test associated with simple Regression on the relationship between school climate and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.421	.581		4.163	.000
	School Climate	.934	.019	.879	48.376	.000

Table 5 revealed that school climate is related with entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria by 0.879. The t-test value 48.376 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between climate change and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test associated with simple Regression on the relationship between teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.822	.711		6.784	.000
	Teaching Strategy	.854	.024	.809	36.162	.000

Table 6 revealed that teaching strategy is related with entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria by 0.809. The t-test value 36.162 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between teaching and learning facilities and entrepreneurship education achievement in senior secondary schools

From the study, teaching and learning facilities predicts 85.2% of students' academic achievement in entrepreneurial education, while 14.8% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study. Also, there is a significant relationship between teaching and learning facilities and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study corroborates with Akomolafe and Adesua (2016) who reported that there was a significant relationship between physical facilities and students' level of motivation and academic performance. This assertion concurs with the outcome of the present study. Nevertheless, availability of physical facilities for learning in schools can serve as motivation towards students' learning. Usen (2016) confirmed the findings of the present

study, as he revealed that there exists significant positive relationship between teachers' utilization of school facilities (library, laboratory, information and communication technology (ICT) center and recreation center) and academic achievement of student nurses in Human Biology. The implication is that when a school is provided with the necessary and adequate teaching and learning facilities and the students are taught with such, the students achieve higher performance.

Relationship between school climate and entrepreneurship education achievement in senior secondary schools

However, school climate predicts 77.3% of students' academic achievement in entrepreneurial education, while 22.7% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study. Also, there is a significant relationship between school climate and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Fakunle and Ale (2018) who reported that there was a significant difference between students' academic performances in schools having open climate and the academic performance of students in schools having controlled climate. This agrees with the findings of this present study and implies that, a favourable climate will go along to enhance job performance, as well as advance students' academic achievement.

Relationship between teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education achievement in senior secondary schools

Further, teaching strategy predicts 65.5% of students' academic achievement in entrepreneurial education, while 34.5% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study. Also, there is a significant relationship between teaching strategy and entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Ganyaupfu, (2013) found that teacher-student interactive method was the most effective teaching method, followed by student-centered method while the teacher-centered approach was the least effective teaching method. This assertion concurs to the outcome of the present study. This implies that attention should be given to the teachers' method of communicating a given subject because; it can go a long way in affecting either positively or negatively to students' performance in a particular subject. However, it is vital to note that students may likely build a better understanding of the main concepts more effectively when they are engaged to solve problems during class activities. Hence, different strategy should be employed in teaching different subjects.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded by establishing the importance of teaching/learning facilities, school climate and teaching strategy that significantly predict the outcome of entrepreneurial education of students. However, when there is adequate and available teaching and learning facilities in schools, it boosts learning among students, thereby enhancing their academic achievement. Nevertheless, when there is enhanced and conducive learning environment, students can understand better, leading to academic achievement. More so, the use of combined teaching and learning strategies will enhance teachers' quality and there by influence students' achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should provide more physical and material resources that are of high quality in public school to motivate students towards learning. Independent entrepreneurs, artisans or even volunteer technical teachers should be engaged to compliment the regular subject teachers.
2. The school management should create and enhance a conducive teaching and learning climate as to ensure efficiency in delivery and high academic performance among teachers and students respectively.
3. The state government should provide all necessary resources and facilities in schools and ensure the effective utilization of these resources in order to enhance academic excellence in schools.
4. Teachers should also increase their knowledge of various instructional strategies through seminars, workshops etc and combined instructional strategies should be employed by teachers

to enhance teaching and learning. This will enable different subject teachers adopt the best strategy that can enhance their teaching and boost students' achievement.

REFERENCES

- Abaidoo, (2018) Factors contributing to academic performance of students. *Global Journal of Educational Research*. 12(2013), 39-45.
- Adalikwe, S. A., & Lorkpilgh, I.T., (2013). The influence of instructional materials on academic performance of secondary school students' performance in chemistry in Cross River State. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 12, 39-45
- Akomolafe, C. O., & Adesua V.O. (2016). The impact of physical facilities on students' level of motivation and academic performance in senior secondary schools in South West Nigeria. *Journal of Education and practice*, 7(4), 38-42
- Ayanyemi, T., (2023) Achievement Education: Meaning and Examples. *Social Science Journal* 6(12), 1-12
- Berkowitz, R., Moore, H., Astor, R.A., & Benbenishty, R., (2017). A research synthesis of the associations between socioeconomic background, inequality, school climate, and academic achievement. *Review Educational Research*, 87(2), 425-469.
- Dean, M. (2019). 10 effective teaching strategies for every classroom. www.classcraft.com
- Fakunle, F.E., & Ale, M.V. (2018). School climate as determinant of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Ekiti state university Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti state. *African Educational Research Journal*, 6(4), 236-239.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). *National policy on Education* .5th Edition NERDC press
- Galvez-Nieto, J.L., Polamco –Levicam, K., Trizano-Hermosilla, I., & Beltran –Veliz, J.C., (2022). Relationship between school climate and values: The Mediating role of attitude towards authority in adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and public Health*. (19), 2726. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052726>.
- Ganyaupfu, E.M. (2013). Teaching methods and students' academic performance. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(9), 29-35
- Héctor A. L. (2015) School performance. *Journal of Education and Innovation*, 3 (1) 313-386.
- Hill, J., & Jordan, L., (2021). Instructional strategies: Design for learning principles, processes and praxis. In J.K., McDonald, & R.E., West. Tech Books. (Eds.) <https://edtech.books.org/id/ir>
- Igocharacha, A.E., Ugochi, L.I., Okolo, O.J., & Egbuionu, O.N. (2017). Managing primary education in a depressed economy. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development (ASERD)*, 9(1), 1-18.
- Knapper, V., (2017). *Actors that influence student academic motivation and how those factors impact the student achievement of third grade students' extrinsic motivation*. Available at; <https://radar.auctr.edu>OBJ> [Accessed 29th July 2024]
- Meindinyo, R.O.K., & Ikurite, N. (2017) Influence of motivation on teacher's performance in a Local Government Area in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 22(5), 22-28
- Opara, E.A. (2018). *Manpower practices, challenges and prospects in Rivers State public secondary schools*. An unpublished dissertation Department of Educational Management. University of Port Harcourt
- Opara, E.A., Okwai, P.N., & Ugwuchi- Ishiaya, J. (2023). Politics of managing education in the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of innovative Education Research*, 11 (1), 87-93
- Ordu, U.B, (2021). The role of teaching and learning aids/methods in a changing world. New challenges to education: Lesson from Around the world. BCES Conference. Books. 202q, 19, Sofia: Bulgarian Comparative Education Society. ISSN 2534-8426 (online)
- Osaat, S.D., & Osaat, D.S. (2013). Undegenerates' perception of entrepreneurial skills acquired for job creation. *International Journal of Research, Innovation and Development*. A publication of university of Port Harcourt